

Mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals. Part-XI. Magnesium-, calcium-, strontium- and barium(II) complexes with 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde and β -diketones

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Manuscript received 16 July 2001, revised 16 October 2001, accepted 20 October 2001

Mg^{II} , Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes of the type $[MLL'(H_2O)_2]$ (where HL = 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde; HL' = pentane-2,4-dione, 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione or 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione) have been synthesized by 1 : 1 : 1 molar reactions of metal chlorides with 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde and β -diketone.

In continuation of our work^{1,2} on the mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals of the type $MLL'(H_2O)_2$, we report here mixed ligand complexes of the type $MLL'(H_2O)_2$, where $M = Mg^{II}$, Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} , HL = 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde (5-ClSalH) and HL' = pentane-2,4-dione (acacH), 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione (bzacH) or 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione (dbzmH).

Results and Discussion

The reactions of hydrated metal ions with 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde and β -diketones, such as pentane-2,4-

dione, 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione or 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione were carried out in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios to give mixed ligand complexes (I).

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the mixed ligand complexes*

Compd.	Decomp. temp. °C	Metal % : Found (Calcd.)
[Mg(5-ClSal)(acac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	240	7.70 (7.72)
[Mg(5-ClSal)(bzac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	205–240	6.41 (6.45)
[Mg(5-ClSal)(dbzm)(H ₂ O) ₂]	148	5.52 (5.42)
[Ca(5-ClSal)(acac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	100–120	12.10 (12.12)
[Ca(5-ClSal)(bzac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	140	10.28 (10.21)
[Ca(5-ClSal)(dbzm)(H ₂ O) ₂]	280	8.87 (8.81)
[Sr(5-ClSal)(acac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	160–170	23.21 (23.17)
[Sr(5-ClSal)(bzac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	100–120	19.95 (19.90)
[Sr(5-ClSal)(dbzm)(H ₂ O) ₂]	120–140	17.49 (17.44)
[Ba(5-ClSal)(acac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	120–140	32.14 (32.09)
[Ba(5-ClSal)(bzac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	220	28.07 (28.03)
[Ba(5-ClSal)(dbzm)(H ₂ O) ₂]	140–150	24.90 (24.88)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and Cl analyses.

All the yellow coloured mixed ligand complexes (Table 1) are quite stable, however, on heating they decompose. All the complexes are insoluble in water, carbon tetrachloride and chloroform but soluble in methanol and DMSO.

The conductances of the complexes are very low, indicating their non-electrolytic nature. Presence of two coordinated water molecules has been established by TGA studies of similar mixed ligand complexes of Mg^{II} . Metal atom is hexacoordinated in these complexes and probable

geometry may be octahedral. Octahedral geometry for alkaline earth metals has been confirmed by X-ray crystal structure studies of the complexes by previous workers³.

TLC study indicates that these are mixed complexes rather than a mixture of the two corresponding bis-complexes.

IR spectra : The mixed ligand complexes exhibited strong IR bands at 1600–1680 (C=O) and 1500–1580 cm^{-1} (C=C). The $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ bands in the complexes are in the lower region as compared to those of the free ligands. Free 2,4-pentanedione showed bands at 1724 (C=O) and 1608 cm^{-1} (C–O) and 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione showed the corresponding bands at 1724 and 1600 cm^{-1} . On coordination $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ band of β -diketone ligands shifted to lower wavenumber side in the mixed ligand complexes. In the spectra of the mixed ligand complexes of chlorosalicylaldehyde and β -diketones, a progressive decrease in the $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ frequency was observed from acetylacetone to dibenzoylmethane (1675 in case of acac, 1650 for bzac and 1625 cm^{-1} for dbzm). The substitution of methyl group by a phenyl group affects the perturbed C=O band. Holtzclaw and Collman⁴ suggested that a phenyl group attached to a carbonyl group in the ligand might set up an interfering conjugation through a quinoid-like structure decreasing the double bond character of the adjacent carbonyl group. Thus the frequency of the perturbed C=O band is lowered and the strength of metal-oxygen bond is decreased. This was confirmed by the spectrum of $\text{Cu}(\text{bzac})_2$ ⁵, which is known to possess a stronger Cu–O bond.

Weak bands at 400–500 cm^{-1} which were absent in the free ligands, may be attributed to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{O}}$ vibration in the mixed ligand complexes. Coordination of water molecules to metal atom was confirmed by the appearance of weak to medium intensity absorption bands at 220–380 cm^{-1} , which may be assigned to metal coordinated OH-stretching.

¹H NMR spectra : ¹H NMR spectra of free 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde gave aldehydic CH proton signal at δ 10.34, which shifted upfield in the mixed ligand complexes at δ 9.32–9.64. This confirms the coordination of the C=O group of the aldehyde to metal atom. The OH proton peak of free aldehyde disappeared in the mixed ligand complexes, which confirms the binding of metal to phenolic oxygen of these ligands through replacement of hydrogen of OH group.

In free acetylacetone the resonances due to CH_3 and CH protons have been reported at δ 1.99 and 5.54, respectively⁶. In the mixed ligand complexes of acetylacetone $\text{Mg}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3\text{ClCHO})(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCH}_3)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ (II) and

$\text{Ca}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3\text{ClCHO})(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCH}_3)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$, singlets due to CH_3^f protons are observed at δ 1.78 and 1.86, and CH^e proton singlets at δ 5.15 and 5.18 ppm, respectively. Upfield shift of these protons confirms the coordination of acetylacetone ligand to the metal atom. In the NMR spectrum of $\text{Mg}(\text{acac})_2$ these peaks have been reported to shift upfield (CH_3 1.70, CH 5.07) as compared to free acetylacetone. Appearance of a single methyl resonance of acetylacetone moiety in the mixed ligand complexes confirms their octahedral structures in which two *trans*-positions are occupied by two water molecules which might possibly be replaced by DMSO molecules when the complexes are dissolved in the solvent. In *cis*-conformation, two methyl resonances would have been observed as reported by Smith and Wilkins⁷ for the complex $\text{Sn}(\text{acac})_2\text{L}_2$. Substitution of methyl group of acetylacetone by phenyl group causes downfield shift of CH^e proton. In free benzoylacetone, this has been reported⁶ at δ 6.18. In the mixed ligand complexes of benzoylacetone $\text{Mg}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3\text{ClCHO})(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOC}_6\text{H}_5)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ (III) and $\text{Ca}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3\text{ClCHO})(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOC}_6\text{H}_5)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ the singlet due to CH^e is observed at δ 5.99. Thus the upfield shift of this peak is an evidence for the coordination of metal atom to this ligand. Recca *et al.*⁸ reported the CH^e signal at δ 5.88 in $\text{Mg}(\text{bzac})_2$ and in the similar region in other alkaline earth metal benzoylacetates.

(II)

(III)

Similarly, in dibenzoylmethane, substitution of two methyl groups by phenyl groups also causes downfield shift of CH^e proton. In free dibenzoylmethane, this has been reported at δ 6.82. In the mixed ligand complex $\text{Ba}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3\text{ClCHO})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCHCOC}_6\text{H}_5)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$, the singlet due to CH^e was observed at δ 6.34. Thus the upfield shift of this peak confirms the coordination of the metal atom to the ligand.

Appearance of the CH signal of the β -diketones in a region very close to that of the aromatic protons supports the pseudoaromatic character of the ring involving the metal atom and the β -diketone ligand.

In free benzoylacetone, CH_3^f protons have been reported⁶ to appear at δ 2.19. In the mixed ligand complexes $\text{Mg}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3\text{ClCHO})(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOC}_6\text{H}_5)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3\text{ClCHO})(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOC}_6\text{H}_5)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$, these protons exhibited a singlet at δ 1.98 and 1.90, respectively. This peak has been reported in similar region in case of benzoylacetones of alkaline earth metals⁶. Upfield shift of these CH_3^f protons supports the coordination of metal atom to the ligand.

Aromatic protons of benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane moieties were observed in the lower field as compared to those of 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde moiety. The aromatic protons of 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde moiety are more resolved and the splitting pattern can be well interpreted. In the complexes $\text{Mg}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3\text{ClCHO})(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOC}_6\text{H}_5)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3\text{ClCHO})(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOC}_6\text{H}_5)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$, CH^d proton gives a doublet at δ 7.22 and 7.10, and CH^b proton gives a doublet at δ 6.54 and 6.53, respectively. CH^c proton exhibited a singlet at δ 7.53 in the former complex and a multiplet at δ 7.41 in the latter.

Experimental

Pentane-2,4-dione (IDPL) was purified by distillation. 1-Phenylbutane-1,3-dione (Fluka), 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione (SD's) and 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde (Aldrich) were purified by crystallization from ethanol. $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{SrCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{BaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (all Glaxo) and $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (E. Merck) were of A.R. grade.

Mixed ligand complexes of Mg^{II} , Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} : To an ethanolic solution of the metal chloride (4 mmol in 15 ml of ethanol) an ethanolic solution of β -diketone and 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde (in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio) was added. The mixture was stirred for ~1 h at 50–60°. The pH of the mixture was then raised to ~6.0–6.5 by adding 5% aqueous NaOH solution (~1 ml) dropwise with constant stirring, and stirring was continued for 1.5 h. The curdy precipitate obtained was filtered and dried under reduced pressure.

Mg, Ca and Sr were determined volumetrically by an EDTA titration and Ba was determined gravimetrically as barium sulfate. C and H were determined using a Coleman 33 analyzer. Specific conductance was measured at room temperature in methanol by a Systronics 304 instrument using a glass cell having cell constant 1.0 cm^{-1} . IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer and ^1H NMR spectra ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) on a Jeol FX 90Q FT NMR spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as a reference.

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